

Regulation of integration processes of agricultural education, science and industry

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Abstract. It has been outlined the need for the priority development of integrating education, science and industry . The main shortcomings of a new system’s implementation of innovative development in the agrarian sector of the economy, built upon the integrative principles of education, science, and industry, were outlined here. Practical recommendations for improving system’s state regulation mechanisms have been developed. The need for a transition from bilateral integration is identified, where priority is given to selecting a partner for integration (education, science or production) to a tripartite integration, involving interaction among its participants (representatives of education, science or industry initiate the creation of trilateral treaties, laboratories, joint centers or work together in the research and educational complex). The main problems towards the creation of university complexes are analyzed and solutions for overcoming these challenges are offered.

1 Introduction

Today we should consider that educational, scientific and manufacturing integration is one of the most important priority aimed at training of highly qualified specialists who meet with the labour market needs in the condition of innovative economy development. In this case, the effective interaction of universities with individual employers and the labor market, as a whole, requires the development of an integrated strategic partnership of the parties, whose purpose is to combine financial, personnel, material and technical resources for mutually beneficial cooperation.

2 Data and Methods

Solution to the issue of improving state regulation mechanisms of integration processes for the agrarian education, science and business is a complex problem, but its resolution can only be done in terms of innovative model development of the agricultural sector and, mainly, through scientific capacity.

Various aspects of this problem were studied by domestic and foreign research scientists. Among them, we may note such scientists as: A.M. Pugach, O.V. Postupna, T. I. Breslavets [1], F. M. Mamatov [3], S. M. Nikolaenko, V. C. Shebanin

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At the same time, the research, conducted in this field considering its urgency, have not exhausted itself and needs further systematic and scientific analysis.

The objective is to identify the problematic aspects of implementation of a new innovative development system for the agro-industrial sector, created on the basis of integration of agrarian education, agrarian science and agrarian industry. The objective is the enhanced cooperation in the issues of functioning and development of the agrarian education and science between central and local authorities. The goal is to create and theoretically justify the effective state regulation mechanism of integration processes for the agrarian education, science and industry.

3 Results

3.1. The Essence and Characteristics of the agricultural education, science and industry

In the Concept of reforming and development of the agrarian education and science, approved by the Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 6 April, 2011 №. 279-p., was set that the current state of the country's economy requires a new system of innovative development of the agro-industrial sector "agrarian education - agrarian science - agrarian production" and enhanced cooperation between central and local authorities in the issues of functioning and development of agrarian education and science.

The issue in question resulted from:

- the existence of an imperfect system for forecasting the needs of qualified workers and specialists with higher education for the Ukrainian labor market and their retraining;
- about 96% of all expenditures from the state budget are spent for social payments by research institutions and there is a lack of development expenditures for upgrading the facilities of agricultural universities and academic institutions;
- shortcomings of the existing academic institutions' network of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences and higher educational institutions at all levels of accreditation;
- the lack of financing for innovation;
- uncertainties about the priorities for the development of agrarian science at the State level, which cause piecemeal funding of scientific research;
- shortcomings in the formation of public procurement for scientific production and the lack of an effective system for R&D project implementation into agricultural industry;
- inconsistency of the material and technical facilities of the higher agrarian educational institutions, vocational training establishments and scientific institutions for the needs of modern agrarian industry;
- the lack of proper social and living conditions, which results in the absence of motivation to get a qualitative result of their work among the graduates of higher agricultural educational institutions and the employees of the agrarian sector.

The problem solution is possible under the condition of reforming of agrarian education and science using innovative approaches that will allow to increase their quality and performance, to enhance the efficient use of staff and scientific capacity of the industry, to provide the agricultural competitiveness of the national economy and to improve the welfare status of the population.

The purpose of the Concept is to integrate academic and university agro- sciences through reforming of higher agricultural education institutions and scientific institutions of the Ukrainian Academy of Agrarian Sciences engaging their capacity for the creation of regional training scientific-productive complexes, taking into account the natural climatic zones, as educational and scientific centers and staffing centers of the Ukrainian agro-industrial complex [4].

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At the same time, over the last few years, requirements for university education have been tightened up in our country. They are determined both by new conditions of the labor market, and by the increasing role of "lifelong education". There is a growing number of people who are applying for university education. At the same time, the competition is growing between different universities, between universities and other research institutes, between private and public organizations.

Business people, in their turn, begin to make demands on the graduates of vocational training establishments, on what they want them to be. Business success depends on how quickly companies' staff is able to redesign its activity in changing circumstances. That is why domestic business is interested in reforming education: it needs specialized experts, and it is ready to give financial support for their education.

3.2 The prospects of international cooperation for the development of the agricultural education, science and industry

In today's society, the belief is growing that the integration of education, science, and industry is critical to ensuring the competitiveness of personnel. Therefore, the quality of experts of a new generation depends on the level of scientific achievements and creativity.

In our country, the teachers of higher education, scientists and entrepreneurs are aware of the need for further development of various types of activity implemented, including interdisciplinary and practically oriented level.

Ukraine has some experience in bilateral integration, namely: teachers of higher education institutions, as a rule, not only teach but are engaged in research work; there are research institutes as part of many universities, focused on the practical realization of scientific ideas, some higher education institutions are considered to be research universities.

The tradition of tripartite interactions has just begun to form. Initiatives of integration processes in education, science, and industry reflect the socio-economic changes in the state. Higher school and science, altogether with other infrastructures, were forced to change the way of functioning. Large quantity of different educational organizations began to appear, which offered various educational services that go beyond the state standards, but meet modern people's demands, as a rule, on a commercial background [1, p. 10].

It should be noted that in the interaction process of agrarian education, science and industry, bilateral integration dominates in Ukraine, where the benefits of selecting a partner for integration (education, science or industry) depend on the understanding of the fundamental partner's activity, as well as on the understanding of the experience of interaction. Scientific institutions and higher education institutions are more inclined to integration in the fundamental spheres of education and science activities, they definitely give priority to industry in applied activities. Industry gives preference to science, precisely, in research field.

In cases of tripartite interaction among its participants, the leading link is the most frequently allocated: representatives of education, science or industry come up with an initiative to create tripartite contracts, laboratories, joint centers, or cooperation within the scientific and educational complex. In this case, one of the most common forms of integration is the creation of educational, scientific and industrial complexes.

Based on this form, a synergy is achieved from the possibilities of industrial equipment in educational process, targeted research work, and knowledge sharing among teachers, scientists, and producers.

Another type of integration, in which the initiative is taken by industry (for example, a large agrarian enterprise), is the creation of educational programs for training agricultural specialists. "meeting requirements of the customer". Integration complexes on the initiative of scientific institutes and organizations are formed less often in our country .

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Today, in the integration process of agrarian education, science and industry, there are organizational structures as part of the majority of external informal structures. It is precisely the creation of such flexible network structures (innovative clusters), established on the basis of multilateral agreements and joint scientific organizations, higher educational institutions, innovative companies and enterprises, may be considered to be one of the keys for successful operating of integration complexes in the agricultural sector.

From the very beginning agrarian university complexes are considered to be training-scientific clusters with a clearly innovative focus, that are exactly, what the formation of this type should be.

Meeting the challenges of radical modernization of science and education, a clear vertical authority is needed, and it will be possible when scientific institutions join the university, and a complex will be established with the only Head represented by the Rector of University. In this regard, we need an objective determination of the causes that delay the implementation of training-scientific clusters in the form of agrarian university complexes, focused on innovative activities in the agrarian sector.

Consequently, we offer to improve the mechanism of state regulation of integration processes in the field of agrarian education, science and industry on harmonizing the principles of state's interests, business, science and education in the following areas:

- creation and support of integrated research and educational production structures for consolidation of efforts and resources, development of scientific activity in order to ensure qualified staff in accordance with the technological modernization of the industry;
- creation of a network of educational, scientific and educational (business incubators) complexes on the basis of higher educational establishments, scientific institutions and enterprises with the further redesigned training and retraining of specialists of the agrarian industry;
- creation of flexible network structures, innovative clusters in order to develop and implement training and production projects;
- development and maintenance of staff capacity of the scientific and technical complex.

Among the main challenges to the creation of university complexes are the following [3, p. 98]:

Insufficient development of theoretical and methodological and conceptual foundation, their formation and functioning, taking into account the realities of the XXI century: new information technologies, innovative strategies, the crucial role of human assets, etc. Formation of university complexes was earlier offered to carry out by extensive methods with the help of reorganization of universities (academies) in mechanical ways: by joining other individuals or uniting in alliances and associations with them.

The university complex is based on integration activity with leading academic and industrial research institutes and advanced scientific industries of production, and it creates the innovative structures like technology parks.

In the years of market reforms, most of the country's higher agricultural educational institutions implemented a survival strategy, in which, practically, there was no room for research work, their funding was completely cut off from budgetary sources, and enterprises and organizations of the agrarian sector did not have money to conclude the agreements for research works with higher educational establishments

During the years of market reforms, higher education institutions have lost their pre-existing research structures and the teaching staff have lost some skills in doing research studies. There was an endless restructuring of scientific and educational management system at the national level. Until now, there is no effective mechanism of harmonizing the interests of educational institutions, scientific, design and other non-profit organizations that are part of university complexes.

4 Conclusions

Thus, to solve the problems, outlined above, and to mobilize fully the potential, which was laid in the idea of creating agrarian university complexes, in our opinion, is necessary to implement the following system of measures based on the concepts of the clusters' theory:

1. We need to move from a simple mechanical association of educational institutions, scientific, design and other nonprofit organizations to the university complex of that or another type. It is necessary to design each of them taking into account historical preconditions, contemporary situation and long-term perspectives. The clusters' theory is the theoretical basis for the creation of comprehensive structures that reproduce productivity factors (new knowledge, innovations, information, human assets, new information technologies, etc.).

In this regard, we should put the development of training-scientific cluster's concept as the basis of the strategy for implementation of university complexes oriented on the creation and the spread of innovations, based on both new knowledge, of which graduates of higher educational institutions are the bearers, and on various research and technology developments.

2. For the formation of agrarian university complexes, in our opinion, both methodologically and in practical terms, land-grant universities of the USA are of particular interest, that appeared in the second half of the XIX century.

Land-grant universities, that have a special status, solve the following public tasks, which have been given to them by the force of law:

- raising the level of education of the rural people;
- scientific research focus on solving urgent farming problems;
- implementation of R&D projects into agricultural production and the development of the social infrastructure in rural areas [2, p. 307].

3. For the formation of agrarian university complexes this form of education and science integration must be backed up by a system of state support measures, stimulating the entry of educational institutions, scientific, design and other non-profit organizations into it.

Limited budget funds should be sent as targeted investments in creating a common infrastructure for institutions and organizations of the university complex (libraries, laboratory and experimental base, computer, information and telecommunication networks, information and consulting, innovative, legal and exhibition centers, Internet centers and design Bureaux, centers for training retraining of personnel, etc.).

Thus, the tripartite integration of science, education and production is, basically, a key focus in the development of knowledge economy, because it allows for effective overcoming the problem of integrated timely provision of innovative processes.

References

1. Breslavets T. I. "Integration of education, science and industry as part of modern development" / T. I. Breslavets // *Visnik DDFA. Ekonomichni nauki.* - 2014. - №. 2. - pp. 8-16.
2. Osetska D.V. "Fiscal and institutional instruments of development of the agricultural sector in Ukraine" / D.V.Osetska // *Ekonomika AITK.* - 2014. - №. 8. - pp. 95-100.
3. Mamatov F. M. "Integration of education, science and industry as a factor of the innovation economy" / F. M. Mamatov, Z. U. Uzakov // *Onovlennya zmistu, form ta metodiv navchannya i vykhovannya v zakladakh osvity.* - 2013. - Issue 7. - pp. 98-101.

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Public Administration in the 21st Century: Problems and Development Prospects.

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4. Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On approval of the Concept of reformation and development of agrarian education and science" dated April 6, 2011 №. 279-p. - Mode of access: <http://zakon1.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/279-2011-/D1/80>.